

Skills 4 EOSC

D2.8 Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework - Final version

Lead Partner:	HK-Dir
Version:	1.0
Status:	Final version
Dissemination Level:	PU: Public
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14933037
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14933037

Deliverable Abstract

This report presents Deliverable 2.8, the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework for trainers' accreditation and recognition. The deliverable is part of the work of Task 2.5, but it builds on and consolidates the outputs of the other WP2 tasks. The recommendations in this deliverable have been piloted by Task 2.3 in their delivery of the FAIR-by-design methodology training and by Task 3.1 in their delivery of training-of-trainers.

These recommendations will inform all training pilots conducted in Work Packages 3 to 5, aiding in the design of future training programs. Additionally, they aim to guide other organisations seeking to formalise their Open Science training initiatives.

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

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DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
v.0.1	14.10.2024	Basic structure of final version	Katrine Weisteen Bjerde
v.0.2	24.11.2024	Final version for internal review	Katrine Weisteen Bjerde + list above
v.0.3	10.01.2025	Final version with reviewers comments	Katrine Weisteen Bjerde + Sonja Filiposka
v.0.4	11.02.2025	Final version with external reviewers' comments	Katrine Weisteen Bjerde + Sonja Filiposka
v.0.5	24.02.2025	Final version before publishing	Katrine Weisteen Bjerde + Sonja Filiposka
V.1.0	28.02.2025	Final review	Claudio Prandoni + Sara Di Giorgio

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology	Definition
Digital credential	Digital credentials are the digital equivalent of paper-based credentials. A digital credential is a proof of qualification, competence, or clearance that is attached to a person.
Micro-credential	Micro-credential means the record of the learning outcomes that a learner has achieved following a small volume of learning. These learning outcomes have been assessed against transparent and clearly defined standards [R1].
Digital badge	Digital badges are a validated indicator of accomplishment, skill, quality or interest that can be earned in various learning environments. According to Shields & Chugh [R2]: "digital badges are quickly becoming an appropriate, easy and efficient way for educators, community groups and other professional organisations to exhibit and reward participants for skills and competences obtained in professional development or formal and informal learning".

Open Badge	Open Badges [R3] are digital credentials based on an open technical specification, the Open Badge standard [R4]. They are a type of open digital credential that is designed to recognise a variety of skills, knowledge, and experiences [R3].
Acronym	Definition
CC	Creative Commons
CI	Continuous Improvement
EC	European Commission
EDC	European Digital Credentials for Learning
EDEH	European Digital Education Hub
EDEN	European Distance and e-learning Network
ELM	European Learning Model
ELMO	ELMO is an implementation of the European (CEN) standards ELM-AI (European Learner Mobility – Achievement Information, EN 15981) and MLO (Metadata for Learning Objects, EN 15982). It is an XML-based format and latest version contains courses, diplomas, Micro-credentials etc.
EMMA	European Multiple MOOC Aggregator
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations
EU	European Union
EUDI	EU Digital Identity Wallet
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICDL	International Computer Driving Licence
IT	Information Technologies
LMS	Learning Management System
LPI	LINUX Professional Institute
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MVS	Minimum Viable Skills
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NI4OS	National Initiatives for Open Science
OBERRED	Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of skills

	in Research Data management and sharing
ODI	Open Data Institute
OECD	Organisation of Economic Co-operation and Development
OS	Open Science
PDF	Portable Document Format
QR code	Quick Response code
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
TOPS	Transform to Open Science
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

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Executive summary

As learners engage with Open Science training, the recognition of their achievements, as well as the accreditation of the trainers delivering this education, becomes increasingly important. Establishing a robust framework for acknowledging both learners' accomplishments and trainers' contributions is essential to fostering a culture of openness and collaboration within the scientific community. Such a framework not only motivates participants but also ensures the credibility and quality of Open Science practices. In order to achieve a harmonised approach across Europe, the trainers must be able to document their training skills in different areas of Open Science. It must be possible to present this documentation to institutions and organisations across Europe. This document presents the final version of the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework for Open Science trainers, and builds on deliverable 2.4 from Task 2.5 in the Skills4EOSC project.

Chapter 1 focuses on what a recognition framework is and its purpose. We also describe how this framework builds on the work and the outputs of other tasks in Skills4EOSC.

Chapter 2 describes the process we followed to create this deliverable. This includes a targeted review of existing trainer accreditation approaches in Open Science and RDM, meetings with some of the most promising projects and groups, and finally internal and external review of the drafts for the framework, following the co-creation procedure laid out by task 2.6.

In Chapter 3, we present the two solutions chosen for digital credentials for the Skills4EOSC courses. These are Open Badges and European Digital Credentials for Learning. The most important characteristics and differences between the two are presented, and we also describe how both options are used and evaluated in the Skills4EOSC project.

Chapter 4 presents a SWOT analysis of the solutions we propose. We look at the risks in the choices we have made and the opportunities going forward. We discuss how the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework can be sustained

after the project ends. Measures could be relevant also for other, similar frameworks and include ensuring long-term maintenance, certification criterion, and setting up a trainer registry. We also discuss possible measures to increase the uptake of the proposal by institutions beyond the Skills4EOSC project.

Chapter 5 delves deeper into the issue of sustainability. We have seen too often that maintaining deliverables from a project after the project end date is a significant challenge, and we wanted to spend more time on exploring how we can ensure lasting effects. We propose using the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network and connection to the EOSC Association. We also point to the need for long-term funding and for ensuring that the recommended technical solutions will continue to be available.

Chapter 6 summarises the recommendations made throughout the report with regards to recognition and certification of trainers. We give recommendations to other tasks within Skills4EOSC and for the period after the project ends. We also outline plans for further work in Task 2.5 for the rest of the Skills4EOSC project.

Chapter 7 contains a set of guidelines on how the recognition framework can be implemented by project partners and external stakeholders. It also provides information about how the credentials can be used by learners.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Recognition Framework

The widespread availability of highly skilled Open Science and data professionals is a pre-condition for the paradigm shift towards Open Science. For this to happen, such skills must be recognised and rewarded. This is reflected in the first General objective (GO1) of the EOSC Partnership Monitoring Framework [R5]: *Open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the “new normal”.*

One of the call objectives of the INFRA-EOSC call that Skills4EOSC stems from is to “Engage with the relevant stakeholders to co-create, promote, broker and ensure the recognition of digital career profiles specifically related to OS.” This is reflected in Objective 1 of the Skills4EOSC project description:

O1 - Map career profiles related to Open Science and define, through co-creation, the “Minimum Viable Skillset” (MVS) for each of them; create a shared framework for the recognition of competences acquired by university students, trainers, and new professionals as a part of an academic path or a lifelong learning process.

The development of the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework contributes to fulfilling these key objectives.

Trainers trained either during the project’s lifetime or later should be able to document their skills to institutions and organisations across Europe. In this deliverable, we recommend a method for providing such documentation through digital credentials awarded after completion of Skills4EOSC training courses.

1.2 Relation to other parts of Skills4EOSC

Skills4EOSC is designed with eight interconnected work packages in which all inform the others in support of project objectives and outputs. The title of Task 2.5 is **Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework for learning materials quality assurance, certification, and trainers’ accreditation**. The focus of

this deliverable is trainer accreditation, as quality assurance and certification of materials is covered by task 2.4.

The Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework is created based on the following deliverables from other tasks in the project as depicted in Fig. 1:

- The set of profiles for various EOSC actors that might need upskilling in Open Science, which are mapped to Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) for each such profile (delivered by task 2.1) [R6]
- The FAIR-by-design methodology for developing training materials (delivered by task 2.3) [R7]
- The method for quality assurance of training materials (delivered by task 2.4) [R8]
- The actual learning material for trainers of the different profiles (to be delivered by work packages 3, 4 and 5 and developed according to the FAIR-by-design methodology and the criteria for quality assurance of training materials)
- Activities designed by work packages 3, 4 and 5 to test the skills acquired through use of the training materials
- The learning platform of Skills4EOSC is available at <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>

Fig. 1 - Relationship between the different outputs from Skills4EOSC

Via the Skills4EOSC Learning Platform, we will issue a digital credential for each course to document the acquired skills as described by the learning objectives. The credentials are currently planned as “one-off”, i.e. there is no validity period, and recipients are not required to renew them after a certain period.

1.3 Contents of the Recognition Framework

The Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework consists of

- this report,
- a set of digital credentials connected to the courses developed for upskilling of Open Science trainers, and
- guidelines for using the framework and adopting it within an organisation.

At this point, the Recognition Framework has been used in two of the Work Packages. In WP2, a three-day train-the-trainer course has been developed for the FAIR-by-design methodology. The course, the digital credentials connected to it, and the evaluation of the pilot is described in more detail in chapter 3. In WP3, a 20 module train-the-trainer course has been developed for training policy makers, civil servants, and knowledge brokers.

More courses will be developed before the end of the Skills4EOSC project, and the relevant credentials will then be added to the framework.

1.4 Characteristics of a Recognition framework fulfilling our purpose

Although the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework is designed for use only within the lifetime of the Skills4EOSC project, it should also be suitable for adoption by institutions across Europe who wish to educate and give recognition to Open Science trainers. Such a framework should therefore have the following characteristics:

- **Flexible:** It should be possible for institutions across Europe to use those parts of the framework that suit their needs and to adapt the courses and the framework to their own context.

- **Inexpensive:** Ideally, use of the framework should be free or at least inexpensive. It should be possible for institutions to implement the framework without high additional costs within training platforms currently in use. Cost must also not prohibit people from taking the training.
- **Easy to implement:** Use of the technical parts of the framework should be as easy as possible to implement. Technical solutions should be based on open standards.
- **Trustworthy:** It should be possible for an individual to store the documentation of their skills in a safe way and easily share to allow for third parties to validate the correctness of the documentation.

2 Creation process

The contents of this document are the result of an initial landscaping and a co-creation process with both internal and external comments.

2.1 Landscaping and selection

The task began with a targeted landscaping review focused on materials relevant to skill recognition and certification. The team also examined frameworks from other domains and explored various accreditation models. A more detailed overview of the most relevant initiatives from the landscaping, including all references, can be found in Appendix 1.

In a second step, we identified organizations experienced in using the most relevant solutions, in order to gather feedback for potential implementation within the project. These discussions helped to justify the choice of two solutions deemed most relevant in the context of the Recognition Framework: Open Badges and European Digital Credentials for Learning (EDCs).

- Open Badges are electronic documents describing that the owner has certain skills or has achieved certain learning outcomes through non-formal or informal learning context. It is a well-established open standard, first launched in 2011. The standard requires minimal effort to be implemented, allowing any organisation to easily start using Open Badges as a certification method for their courses. Open Badges was already well known to the task group from the European OBERRED project. In the landscaping process we also saw that this solution was used in several other cases we examined (NASA, EOSC Future, DC4EU) and it has been implemented as an integral part of a broad range of learning platforms.
- EDCs are standardised, tamper-evident electronic documents describing learning skills or achievements obtained in a wide variety of settings from micro credentials to university degrees. EDC is a document format based on the open standard European Learning Model (ELM) [R9]. It is the main European Commission (EC) initiative

for handling digital credentials and micro-credentials. EDC is relatively new (launched October 2021) but the standard is gradually being adopted by more and more projects (eg. DocTalent4EU), HE institutions, national initiatives and authorities and University alliances.

The Open Badges and EDC are explained in more detail in chapter 3 Recommended solutions.

2.2 External review and revision

Drafts of the deliverable have been subject to a co-creation and validation process where both internal and external reviewers have commented on the drafts. Their comments have been taken into account in the final published version.

The feedback from the co-creation survey [R10] that was provided together with the first version of the deliverable highlights a strong interest in creating a flexible and impactful recognition framework for Open Science training accomplishments. Although most of the respondents already have practical familiarity with Open Badges, they suggested implementing both Open Badges and EDCs, offering participants a choice based on their needs. Several comments also addressed the need for a sustainable and authoritative structure to ensure the legitimacy and continuity of the recognition process. Suggestions included recognizing competence centres as entities authorized to issue digital credentials. Additionally, feedback pointed out the necessity of keeping skills repositories up to date and focusing on the actual skills embedded in the credentials, ensuring that they provide real value to learners and organizations. The overarching concern was that credentials should not be used superficially but should have meaningful impacts on training and management practices.

3 Recommended solutions

3.1 Digital credentials in general

The first version of digital credentials came as PDF versions of the traditional paper-based credentials, but these have limited possibilities for machine readability and other forms were quickly developed.

Digital credentials are digital representations of a person's skills, knowledge, or qualifications [R11]. In the context of this Recognition Framework, they are considered to be issued by organisations to describe the learning achievement from completing a learning unit. Unlike traditional paper-based certificates, digital credentials are:

- **Verifiable:** The authenticity and validity of digital credentials can be checked online using different secure methods.
- **Portable:** They can be easily shared and accessed from any device with an internet connection.
- **Secure:** Digital credentials can be protected from fraud and tampering.
- **Flexible:** They can represent a wide range of qualifications, from formal education to informal learning experiences.

Fig. 2 - Description of the credentials ecosystem

Micro-credentials are a specific type of digital credential that focus on a narrow skill or knowledge area [R1]. Although definitions of micro-credentials vary, in the context of the Recognition Framework we use them to describe learning that is small in volume, assessed in some way, and associated with a digital certification. They can be earned through online courses, workshops, or other learning experiences. Micro-credentials can be used to demonstrate proficiency in a particular skill or to supplement a formal education. Their key characteristics include:

- **Specialised:** Micro-credentials focus on a specific skill or knowledge area.
- **Low volume:** They are typically earned through short programs or courses.
- **Stackable:** Micro-credentials can be combined to demonstrate a broader range of skills or knowledge.
- **Flexible:** They can be earned through a variety of learning modalities, including online and in-person.

Although initially micro-credentials were intended for informal and non-formal settings only, today they are accepted as a way of augmenting formal digital credentials with specific skills that may also be obtained in a formal educational environment, and in some cases may come with defined ECTS. Thus, they are deemed to have a great potential for describing the skills and learning achievements obtained as part of the lifelong learning.

To issue digital credentials and/or micro-credentials a suitable framework needs to be chosen to ensure the security, authenticity, and portability of these credentials. To ensure sustainability and alignment, it must be ensured that the chosen solution adheres to the requirements set by the European Commission [R1]: “The proof [of credential] is contained in a certified document that lists the name of the holder, the achieved learning outcomes, the assessment method, the awarding body and, where applicable, the qualifications framework level and the credits gained. Micro-credentials are owned by the learner, can be shared, are portable and may be combined into

larger credentials or qualifications. They are underpinned by quality assurance following agreed standards.”

In this recognition framework we propose the use of two leading frameworks for issuing digital credentials and micro-credentials: Open Badges and European Digital Credentials for Learning (EDCs) that offer distinct advantages and can be used in various contexts to provide verifiable and portable representations of skills and knowledge.

3.2 Description of Open Badges

Open Badges are digital credentials based on an open technical specification, the Open Badges standard. They are a type of open digital credential that is designed to recognise a variety of skills, knowledge, and experiences.

The Open Badges standard is managed by the 1EdTech [R12] organisation and is implemented as part of a broad range of learning platforms. Since its initial release in 2011, the standard has undergone a number of revisions, with the latest one being Open Badges 3.0, published at the end of December 2024.

Structurally, Open Badges are represented as images which contain embedded metadata describing the skills and achievements that the badges represent, as well as information on the issuing organization and the recipient. This provides a transparent, digital verification of what has been learned and evidence of that learning. Figure 3 provides a visual overview of Open Badges contents. The Open Badge can be seen as a visual representation of skills.

OPEN BADGES

Data & Information **Inside**

- | | |
|-------------------|-----------------|
| Alignment | Expiration Date |
| Badge Criteria | Issued Date |
| Badge Description | Issuer |
| Badge Name | JSON-LD |
| Digital Signature | Recipient |
| Evidence | Verification |

Fig. 3 - Open Badge content by 1EdTech, licensed under CC-BY-4.0

An important aspect of any digital credential is the way in which its authenticity can be established. Verification of the embedded metadata describing an Open Badge can be done in one of two ways:

- via the issuer, validating that the metadata present in the badge image has not been tempered with and corresponds to the actual data as stored by the issuing party.
- self-validation, by verifying the signature used to digitally sign the badge.

The most common approach in practice today is the first one, where the verification of the digital credential depends on the availability of the issuer’s infrastructure. This is also the approach taken by many popular learning management systems when it comes to their support of Open Badges.

The self-validation option is new in the version 3.0 of the Open Badges standard and has not been widely adopted yet. We assume, however, that adoption will be quick, as this feature will ensure important compatibility with upcoming digital wallets, including the EU Digital Identity Wallet.

Table 1 Key considerations for Open Badges

Pros	Cons
Portability Badges can be easily shared and	Value Some employers may not yet

verified across different platforms and institutions.	recognize the value of digital badges, especially compared to traditional qualifications.
<p>Simplicity</p> <p>Open Badges is already implemented in a broad range of learning platforms, and the threshold for starting to use them is fairly low.</p>	<p>Interoperability</p> <p>Ensuring interoperability between different badge systems can be complex.</p>
<p>Transparency</p> <p>The open standard and verifiable nature of Open Badges increases transparency and trust.</p>	<p>Quality</p> <p>There is a risk of badge inflation or the issuance of low quality-content badges.</p>
<p>Customisation</p> <p>Badges can be highly customised to reflect specific learning outcomes or achievement levels.</p>	<p>Recognition</p> <p>Although many HEIs award Open Badges and are aware of their potential, widespread adoption and formal recognition in the HE sector varies.</p> <p>More widespread among informal education providers.</p>

3.3 Description of European Digital Credentials for Learning

European Digital Credentials for Learning (EDCs) is the main European Commission (EC) initiative for handling digital credentials and micro-credentials. They are a standardised form of digital certification that can be recognised across the European Union (formal recognition is dependent upon the laws of each member state). These credentials can represent educational qualifications, skills, or professional achievements and are designed to be interoperable across borders and institutions within the EU.

The system has been in production since 2022 but new extensions are continuously being developed.

EDCs are issued by verifiable institutions and include standardised metadata, ensuring consistency and interoperability across the EU. The credentials can be multi-lingual, and they are verified through a secure digital infrastructure supported by the European Commission, and must be signed with an electronic seal, making them trustworthy and easily portable between EU countries. Currently, learners can share their EDCs with potential employers, educational institutions, or other relevant parties via Europass [R13], that serves as the default “wallet” for EDCs. It is expected that EDCs will also be compatible with the upcoming EU Digital Identity Wallets and other wallets can be developed based on the provided open-source.

EDCs can be used for nonformal and informal training, formal education and vocational training. A number of projects, such as DocTalent4EU [R14], are showcasing the versatility of their use.

An EDC is a structured digital document that contains detailed information about a specific qualification or achievement. The elements that are of particular interest to this Recognition Framework are:

- Issuing information such as who is the issuer
- Learner information with the main personal details
- Credential details that describe the qualifications it represents including a list of the learning outcomes and related assessment methods.
- Verification Information that can be used to validate the credential.
- Metadata that further describes the credential
- Electronic signature that verifies the authenticity and integrity of the credential.

The structure of an example EDC is presented in the image below.

Fig. 4 -EDC structure; image taken from

<https://europa.eu/europass/en/stakeholders/european-digital-credentials>

To be able to issue EDCs an organisation must first obtain an eSeal (i.e. an electronic signature that is associated with a legal entity) that is used to digitally sign the credentials. Two alternatives are then available. An organisation may choose to use the web EDC application (called the EDC Issuer and Online Credential Builder) provided by the EC, or the organisation may decide to install the open-source framework locally in order to be able to customise it and/or integrate it with other systems aiming to automate the process of issuing the credentials.

Before issuing EDCs, the organisation needs to design one or more credentials that will be issued by:

- clearly defining the type of credential (e.g. certificate) and the specific achievements (learning outcomes) it represents.
- establishing the criteria that learners must meet to earn the credential.
- developing additional metadata for the credential, including the issuer, learner information, and relevant details.

Fig. 5 - The European Learning Model; image by Europass taken from <https://europa.eu/europass/en/node/2128>

EDCs offer issuers the freedom to define the level of detail in their learning outcome descriptions. By utilizing the European Learning Model (ELM) [R9] as a foundation, issuers can choose from a vast array of optional metadata elements. This flexibility allows for both standardized descriptions using frameworks such as ESCO skills (which are used in the MVS profiles developed by Skills4EOOSC) and highly customized representations. Ultimately, the issuer retains control over the granularity and specificity of the EDC description.

Once the template is defined, the organisation can issue the EDC to a pre-prepared list of recipients. Each issued EDC will be digitally signed using the eSeal. The learner will then receive the EDC that can be stored within Europass.

The complete process for issuing EDCs is well described and documented on the main EU EDC pages under Europass tools [R15]. In addition, the EDC team is always available to answer questions and help with any type of inquiries.

Table 2 Key considerations for EDCs in the context of the Recognition Framework

Pros	Cons
<p>Political support and standardisation</p> <p>Provides a consistent framework for recognizing qualifications across Europe. The solution has strong support from the European Commission.</p>	<p>Integration and automation</p> <p>Credentials issuing is currently a fairly manual process. Integrating EDC with existing learning systems and processes needs to be implemented by the issuer. Integration with popular learning platforms is currently still under development.</p>
<p>Trustworthy</p> <p>Credentials are signed using an electronic seal, thus ensuring they are tamper-evident.</p>	<p>Bureaucracy</p> <p>The process of acquiring the necessary eSeal and issuing and verifying EDCs can be time-consuming.</p>
<p>Interoperability</p> <p>Are potentially recognized across all EU member states, facilitating mobility and cross-border employment.</p>	<p>Complexity</p> <p>More complex compared to open digital badges, particularly when targeting informal learning achievements.</p>
<p>Compatibility</p> <p>Can easily be aligned with national and EU-level qualifications frameworks and the ESCO skills vocabulary.</p>	<p>Limited operating systems support</p> <p>The online EDC Issuer is currently supporting only Microsoft systems when using the eSeal to issue credentials.</p>

3.4 Comparison between Open Badges and EDCs

In the table below, we compare the characteristics of Open Badges and EDC against the requirements for a good recognition framework listed in section 1.4. These are highly desired characteristics of a recognition framework and are used to evaluate the two solutions.

Table 3 Alignment of Open Badges and EDCs key features with the Recognition Framework requirements

Recognition Framework Requirement	Open Badges	EDCs
Flexibility	Mostly used to represent informal and non-formal learning experiences.	Can be used to represent formal education in addition to informal and non-formal.
	Current implementations provide a high-level description of the achievements in a less structured way.	Include rich and flexible metadata that can be used to capture the details of the learning experience.
	Designed to be interoperable with various systems and platforms, making them widely accepted and recognized.	Compatible with other digital credential systems, facilitating international recognition, while aligned with European regulations.
Inexpensive	The Open Badges standard itself is free and open, anyone can adopt and use it without any cost. There might be costs associated with the use of commercial platforms or	The EC has made the infrastructure for issuing and verifying EDCs open and accessible to all. Organizations can issue EDCs without any licensing fees or subscription costs.

	<p>services used to issue, manage, or display Open Badges. However, there are also many free, open-source solutions as well as integrations with well-known learning platforms.</p>	<p>There is a cost for acquiring the eSeal needed to issue the EDCs. This varies depending on the country and issuer.</p> <p>If you choose to use the open-source software and implement EDC locally, there are costs related to setting up and maintaining a local infrastructure and integration with learning platforms (as this is not yet available from the EC).</p>
<p>Easy to implement</p>	<p>Based on an open standard, technical expertise and development is required if you want to implement from scratch.</p> <p>However, many readily available user-friendly tools and platforms already exist.</p>	<p>Good understanding of the underlying data model is required when developing credential templates.</p> <p>EC provides a user-friendly platform and detailed guidelines to facilitate the definition and issuing of EDCs.</p> <p>Using a local installation that allows for more automation, requires much higher technical expertise.</p>
<p>Trustworthy</p>	<p>Earned badges can be stored in personal digital wallets or backpacks with personal control over the credentials and with whom</p>	<p>Individuals can store their EDCs in Europass, then choose to share them with authorized parties.</p> <p>When an institution issues</p>

	<p>they share them.</p> <p>Open Badges can be issued as digitally signed documents that can be independently verified. When following the newest standard, the structured data within Open Badges enables automated verification and recognition by systems.</p>	<p>an EDC, it applies an eSeal to the digital document. This eSeal acts as a digital signature, certifying the origin and authenticity of the credential. A recipient can verify the eSeal to confirm that the credential has not been altered or compromised.</p> <p>The eSeal is regarded as more secure than the digitally signed Open Badges.</p>
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The choice between Open Badges and EDCs depends on the specific needs and goals of the issuer. When in need of a flexible and widely recognised credentials system that focuses on non-formal and informal learning, Open Badges may be a good option. If one needs a credential that is aligned with European regulations EDCs may be more suitable, and if you want to issue formal credits (ECTS), using EDCs is clearly your easiest option.

In many cases, it may be possible to use a combination of Open Badges and EDCs. For example, an organisation could start off issuing Open Badges for informal learning experiences and then later decide to go for EDCs for more formal education qualifications. Once an institution decides to go for EDC for formal credentials, it seems to make sense to use it for all credentials, but the choice and the flexibility is still there.

3.5 Pilot implementations within Skills4EOSC

3.5.1 Open Badges pilot

Within Skills4EOSC the first Open Badges pilot was implemented for the FAIR-by-design methodology course [R16]. Based on recommendations from Task 2.5, the project-wide training was extended to allow participants to earn badges that can be used as verifiable digital credentials.

In collaboration with GARR, the Skills4EOSC learning platform has been certified as an Open Badges v2.0 issuer, ensuring that the issued badges are compatible with other badge systems. To facilitate the collection and sharing of badges, the learning platform was connected to the Badgr backpack [R17], a popular solution for storing and displaying badges. This allows users to easily organize and manage their badges obtained from various training activities.

A hierarchical group of stackable open badges was defined for the training. Lower-level badges can be earned by completing specific stages of the FAIR-by-design methodology, while the overarching higher-level badge can only be earned by stacking all the lower-level badges, i.e. completing the entire training.

Fig. 6 – Open Badges for the FAIR-by-Design methodology training

Each badge description contains the list of the learning outcomes that need to be achieved for the particular badge. To assess whether the training participant has managed to reach the learning objectives, each learning unit in the training is accompanied with assessment. To obtain a stage-specific open badge (one of the lower-level badges in Fig. 6), all learning units associated with that stage need to be successfully completed. The stacked higher-level open badge named “FAIR Instructor” is issued to training participants that have successfully obtained all stage-specific badges. By obtaining the FAIR Instructor open digital badge, the participant is certified as able to put the complete FAIR-by-design methodology into practice, thus becoming a FAIR instructional designer.

This approach has also been adopted in Skills4EOSC WP3 for the 20 modules of the train-the-trainer course for training the profiles policy makers, civil servants

and knowledge brokers. The first round of training has been delivered, and Open Badges will be issued as soon as the assignments submitted by the trainees have been evaluated. For instance, participants earn individual badges for completing modules such as Data Stewardship Fundamentals and Metadata Standards. A final "Open Science Trainer" badge is awarded to those achieving all module-specific badges, recognizing comprehensive mastery.

3.4.2 Planned EDC pilot

As Italy's National Research and Education Network (NREN) and project coordinator, GARR has taken on the role of central issuer of European Digital Credentials for Learning (EDC) for all training activities within the Skills4EOSC project. This centralized approach ensures consistency and reliability in certifying competencies acquired through the project's various training initiatives. While this implementation serves also as a pilot experience in the context of European projects, its primary goal is to provide participants with official, legally valid digital credentials certifying their acquired competencies in Open Science related skills.

GARR has acquired a qualified electronic seal from an accredited Italian certification authority. The technical implementation has been tested and validated through the European Union's playground environment (not available since January 2025), allowing GARR to refine the workflow before moving to production.

The credential issuance workflow has been standardized across the project through the development of a common template. This template includes agreed-upon data fields that trainers must complete, ensuring consistency in credential information across all project training activities. The standardized approach simplifies the certification process while maintaining the quality and completeness of the credentials issued. Credentials will be designed using the Online Credential Builder [R18] and then issued using the EDC Issuer, both available on the dedicated EU platform.

At the time we submit this report, the actual issuance of credentials has not been started, but the planned process follows these steps:

1. Project trainers input the required information into the standardized template, including specific competencies achieved and learning outcomes.
2. GARR personnel review the submitted information for completeness and accuracy and upload them using the Online Credential Builder.
3. The credential is prepared using the validated template.
4. GARR applies the qualified electronic seal, providing legal validation of the credential.
5. The sealed credential is issued through the EDC infrastructure, making it available to the recipient through their Europass profile.

The initial testing phase in the EU playground environment¹ was crucial in validating our approach. This testing covered the entire workflow, from template creation and data input to the sealing process and final issuance. The experience gained during this phase has helped refine the procedures and identify potential issues before full implementation.

The standardized template developed for the Online Credential Builder includes carefully selected data fields that capture the essential information about the training activities. This includes:

- Specific competencies acquired
- Learning outcomes aligned with European frameworks
- Training duration and modality
- Assessment methods and results
- Open Science specific skills and knowledge areas

This centralized issuance model, supported by robust technical solutions and standardized templates, ensures that all Skills4EOSC training activities result in consistent, legally recognized digital credentials. The experience gained through the playground testing and template development could provide valuable insights for other organizations planning to implement similar digital credential systems.

¹ The playground environment was discontinued from January 2025, but the Online Credentials Builder is still available.

4 SWOT analysis of the Recognition Framework

In this chapter we look at the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats associated with the use, further adoption and maintenance of the Recognition Framework based on the combination of OBs and EDCs.

Although the EDC pilot has not yet been carried out in the production environment, the experience from the testing in the EC Playground environment has given us enough material for use in this SWOT analysis.

Strengths

- **Strong foundation:** The framework is based on a landscaping analysis followed by an internal and external co-creation process. We believe this procedure has ensured that all relevant solutions have been considered.
- **Well-established technical solutions:** Open Badges and European Digital Credentials are both recognised and used standards managed by well-established organisations. Technical solutions that support both options should continue to be available in the foreseeable future. The EU Digital Identity Wallet will support verifiable credentials using the ELM format and has created a converter from the Open Badges format to ELM.
- **Potential for broad adoption:** The choice to support both the Open Badges and EDC formats can facilitate integration with various learning platforms.
- **Alignment with EOSC goals:** The framework supports the development of Open Science skills in a lifelong learning context, opening the possibility for both formal and non-formal micro-credentials.

Weaknesses

- **Dependency on external organisations:** The framework relies on uptake by accredited bodies or educational institutions for formal certification, or on the network of Competence Centres for non-formal

and informal certification.

- **Limited funding:** The long-term sustainability of the framework depends on securing adequate funding.
- **Possible lack of uptake:** The framework is currently not well known and may face challenges in gaining widespread adoption among competence centres and research institutions.

Opportunities

- **Collaboration with the EOSC Association:** Partnering with the EOSC Association can enhance the framework's visibility and sustainability.
- **Leveraging Competence Centre network:** The Open Science Competence Centre network that is being established through Skills4EOSC can play a crucial role in maintaining and promoting the framework.
- **Integration with emerging standards:** Aligning with European Commission's standard European Digital Credentials can help expand the framework's reach and flexibility.
- **Registry of trainers:** A well-maintained registry of qualified trainers can facilitate connections between trainers and institutions, fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration.
- **Clear conditions for receiving a digital credential:** Clearly defined criteria can enhance the credibility and value of digital credentials, motivating learners to achieve the required competencies.

Threats

- **Changing landscape of Open Science:** The evolving nature of Open Science will require regular adaptations of the framework.
- **Lack of quality assurance:** If connection to a central authority with clearly defined mandate is not established, ensuring consistent quality standards for digital credentials may be difficult.
- **Technical challenges:** Maintaining a system that supports both Open Badges and European Digital Credentials requires technical expertise and resources.
- **Competing standards:** The emergence of alternative standards or

approaches could challenge the dominance of Open Badges and European Digital Credentials.

To mitigate the identified weaknesses and threats, a strategic approach is necessary. By focusing on diversification, collaboration, and technological awareness, the framework can enhance its sustainability, broaden its reach, and solidify its position in the Open Science landscape.

By including both Open Badges and European Digital Credentials as viable options, the Recognition Framework will benefit from the strengths of each standard while mitigating potential risks associated with relying solely on one. We see this approach as enhancing the framework's flexibility, adaptability, and long-term sustainability.

Diversification involves exploring diverse funding sources, partnering with multiple institutions via the Competence Centre Network to be able to develop common, but also individual internal certification mechanisms for specific skills.

Collaboration with key stakeholders like the EOSC Association, other Competence Centres, and HEIs can significantly amplify the framework's impact. By leveraging collective expertise and resources and ensuring a common, aligned approach, the framework can address challenges more effectively.

Technological awareness must be demonstrated by following the developments of the chosen solutions (Open Badges and EDC), adapting the framework to new versions and also following the emergence of new standards.

More on how to build on the strengths and mitigate the risks is found in chapters 5 and 6.

5 Sustainability

Sustainability beyond the lifetime of the Skills4EOSC project, which ends in August 2025, is seen as the most significant risk for the adoption and future maintenance of the framework. This challenge deserves its own chapter.

5.1 Responsibility beyond the project timespan

Maintenance of the framework and issuance of the trainer certifications is best done by a single and recognised authority within the EOSC governance framework. However, once the project ends, the centralised umbrella of the Skills4EOSC project will cease to exist.

We suggest that the responsibility for maintenance of the Recognition Framework after the project ends, lies with the Competence Centre network that Skills4EOSC will create. WP7 will create a lightweight mechanism to ensure such a network through effective coordination between the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres. The project management is in discussions with the EOSC Association and with the EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group no 5 [R18] on how this can be achieved.

Utilising the Competence Centre Network to maintain the Recognition Framework, the following areas from the SWOT analysis could be addressed:

- **Advocacy work:** Both within the project and after project end, advocacy work is vital to achieving uptake of the framework. Several presentations for relevant HE institutions have been carried out and there are more to come. Enrolling members of the Competence Centre Network to continue this work after the project ends will be a priority.
- **Quality Assurance and recognition:** It is advisable that recommended quality and certification parameters are adopted by the issuing institution beyond the Skills4EOSC project. However, this is impossible to monitor without having a central authority in place. During the lifetime of Skills4EOSC, the project will be responsible for updating the Recognition Framework.

After the project ends, the Competence Centre Network or EOSC Association could undertake quality assurance activities and take

responsibility for continued effort to ensure that guidelines for certification are kept updated and to keep the certification criteria harmonized.

- **Trainer registry:** Ensure there is a centralised registry of trainers that is maintained and kept up to date. This would give the trainers more visibility and would make it easier for institutions to contact these trainers for design and/or delivery of trainings to further Open Science skills training in their local context.
- **Updating trainer skills:** Having a permanent responsible authority would open the possibility for trainers to regularly renew their badges with updated skills.

5.2 Long-term funding

As the world of Open Science develops, it will be necessary for the learning materials and Recognition Framework to develop along with it. This will require resources that must come from either the institutions involved or from some other source. At this point in time, we have no clear picture of the resources required or how to fund it. This must be clarified before the end of the Skills4EOSC project.

5.3 Long-term technical solutions

The choice of EDC as one of the credential solutions will ensure political and technical support from the European Commission for the foreseeable future.

The use of Open Badges requires a learning infrastructure that supports this standard. During the Skills4EOSC project (until August 2025), this is in place via the project's learning platform, based on the open-source Moodle learning management system. Open Badges has become a de facto standard for open digital badges, and in addition to Moodle, a long list of learning platforms is already compatible with this standard [R19].

Beyond this project, any organisation wanting to pilot or use the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework would have to either use the same platform or use another learning platform that has enabled the use of Open Badges. That system will need to run for as long as possible enabling learners to verify

their badges, so a long-term operation and support plan needs to be considered.

This might create a barrier for some organisations to use this solution. However, this is a risk we face no matter our proposed solution. The choice to use Open Badges seems to be the solution which currently is least likely to create problems.

6 Recommendations for further work

In this chapter we sum up the recommendations we have given in previous parts of the report for the use and maintenance of the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework.

6.1 Recommendations to ensure sustainability

These recommendations are relevant both for the project management during the project and for the European Commission and the EOSC Association after the project:

- We recommend letting the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network be responsible for managing and maintaining the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework and the accompanying Guidelines after the end of the project.
- We recommend establishing an organisational link between the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network and the EOSC Association.
- We recommend creating a plan for long-term funding of the maintenance activities.
- We recommend creating a registry of accredited Skills4EOSC trainers, subject to limitations of GDPR.
- We also recommend involving the EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group 5 [R18] in planning how to achieve sustainability.

6.2 Recommendations to Skills4EOSC colleagues

Below, we give some recommendations to other work packages in Skills4EOSC tasked with developing training materials:

- We recommend splitting train-the trainer courses into low-volume modules and issue digital credentials (Open Badges and/or EDC) for all trainings. All trainings offered in the Skills4EOSC project should issue at least one digital credential on a course or course module level. If credentials are offered on a module level, consider issuing a higher-level credential for the total course.

- Follow recommended criteria before issuing a credential. Each credential can only be issued after certain conditions are met. Each task organising and delivering the training should set the conditions for when a credential can be awarded, and this should be clearly stated in the information of the training.
- Follow Skills4EOSC credential branding and metadata guidelines. The recommended logos and required information for the metadata are addressed in section 3.5.
- Have a system of peer review in place. For all trainings, as per the FAIR-by-design-methodology, request a partner to check if your training meets the recommended criteria for certification.
- If a Skills4EOSC trainer registry is established, all tasks organising training should make sure all trainers who have received a credential and who consent to being listed, are added to the trainer registry.

6.3 Planned tasks for Task 2.5 until august 2025

The Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework is the main deliverable of Task 2.5, but the task will continue working until the end of the project. For the remaining months of the project, we will focus on the following:

- Continue reaching out to research institutions to inform them of the Recognition Framework and increase the uptake.
- Continue following the development of Open Badges and European Digital Credentials and the ongoing initiatives to establish openly available mappings between EDC and other formats. Update the guidelines to reflect any significant changes.
- In cooperation with the project management, investigate the possibility of a sustainable structure for maintaining the Skills4EOSC Recognition framework through the Competence Centre Network or another structure associated with the EOSC Association. Discussions will also be initiated with EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group 5 [R18].

7 Guidelines for the use of the Framework

To help interested institutions adopt the Recognition Framework, a set of guidelines have been prepared, providing advice from three different perspectives: the learner’s perspective, the course manager’s perspective, and the platform administrator’s perspective.

These parties will have different perspectives on and approaches to the contents of the framework. Relevant recommendations, as well as common pitfalls are explained in each subsection below.

Initially, we provide a table that compares characteristics of Open Badges and European Digital Credentials from the perspective of the Learner and the Issuer (the institution comprising both course administrator and learning platform administrator). This comparison can help issuers decide which digital credential solution they opt for in their courses or (training) programmes.

Before the end of the Skills4EOSC project, these guidelines will be published as a separate document. We will also continue to update the guidelines until the project ends.

	Important Information	Open Badges	European Digital Credentials
1	For Learners (Credential Recipient):		
a	Digital Credential	√	√
b	Need a ‘wallet’ to display credential	√	√
c	No additional cost/fee to receive credential	√	√
d	Portability of skills and competencies (sharing the credential with third-party services such as LinkedIn)	√	√
e	Multi-lingual support	? ²	√

² [Separate Open Badges can be issued for different languages and then linked to indicate that it is actually the same credential](#)

2	For Course Managers (Credential Issuer):		
a	Possibility to Issue Micro-credentials	√	√
b	Criterion for issuance of credential	√	√
c	Design/branding required	√	√
d	Metadata included within credential	√	√ ³
e	Alignment to a URL specifying system/standard	√	√
f	Implemented in a range of learning platforms (Moodle, Blackboard, Canvas, Open edX as well as Coursera, Udemy, etc)	√	
g	Can be used as a formal transcript of records (ECTS)		√
h	Non-accredited education	√	√
3	For Course Administrators		
a	Identity verification	?	? ⁴
b	eSeal required to issue credential		√
c	Additional cost implication		√
d	Defining validity of credential	√	√
e	Self-contained verification	? ⁵	√

7.1 The learner's perspective

Many institutions consider digital credentials from their own perspective and forget that the learner will be the ultimate 'user'. When issuing digital credentials, it is important to keep the learner at the forefront. Learners like to be awarded credentials. It enables them to demonstrate their level and grasp of content of a given topic. They should be able to share these with prospective employers in the future to demonstrate how they meet any particular requirements. A digital credential allows learners to easily do this.

Learners should not be burdened with the technical details of how the credentials are issued. The main concern from the learners' perspective is

³ EDCs have much richer metadata potential than OBs, and the description of learning achievement is very well structured. An OB could be linked to a web page describing more details

⁴ Could be ensured by the course administrators

⁵ Only if digitally signed badges are used and not hosted ones

how widely the offered digital credentials are recognised and what criteria need to be met to earn them. In this manner, learners can be incentivised to enrol in a given course, meet the criteria, and obtain the digital credentials.

Open Badges

Open Badges is a standard that has been around for years and is well known and recognised. It has been implemented in most of the widely used learning platforms.

Backpacks: Open Badges can be shared via a ‘backpack’. Not all learners are familiar with the concept of a ‘backpack’ and could be given tips on how to adopt a personal strategy for downloading, storing and sharing obtained badges.

It is a given that the badge will be available as part of the learner’s personal portfolio on the learning platform where it has been issued, but this might not be publicly accessible or visible to guest users. Learners can download all issued badges locally as image files that will contain the relevant metadata needed for its verification.

Alternatively, learners can opt to use one of the many free and available backpack services [R20] to build a personal badge portfolio. Since all issued badges have a unique public URL associated with them, they can also be included in Europass CVs, along with the downloaded badge image [R21]. Following a similar approach, badges can also be prominently displayed on social media platforms [R22].

Validation: Using the embedded metadata in the badge image file itself, free online validators [R23, R24] can be used to read all relevant details, as well as verify the badge’s validity by anyone, including the badge recipient. Furthermore, should the issued badge be compliant with the Open Badges 3.0 standard, self-verification without contacting the issuer could be possible as well, thus enabling the storing and sharing of the digital credentials using digital wallets such as the EU Digital Identity Wallet [R25, R26].

European Digital Credentials: The introduction of EDCs marks a significant advancement in how learners interact with their qualifications and achievements. Key advantages include:

Ease of Access and Sharing: The Europass Wallet enables learners to manage their credentials independently. Upon receiving an EDC, learners can store it securely in their wallet and share it with prospective employers or institutions as needed. Learners can easily forward their credentials to third parties, such as employers or educational institutions, via secure links or downloadable formats. Integration with platforms like LinkedIn further simplifies the process of showcasing skills and achievements.

Enhanced Trust and Recognition: As EDCs are potentially recognized by a wide set of European institutions and employers, they provide learners with a high level of credibility. The credentials are digitally signed and tamper-evident, ensuring their validity when presented to third parties.

Ease of verification: The digital infrastructure also supports verification, ensuring that the credentials shared are authentic and compliant with European standards. This streamlines the validation process for all stakeholders involved and reinforces trust in the learner's documented achievements.

7.2 The course manager's perspective

Course managers define the strategy with which digital credentials are issued. Common questions which arise during this initial step include: What modules require digital credentials, and would there be dependencies between different digital credentials? At what granularity should the digital credentials be issued, and would there be multiple digital credentials covering the same area designating different levels of understanding (e.g., basic, intermediate, advanced)? Would a final digital credential be issued once all modules of a given course are successfully completed, confirming a participant's completion of the course as a whole?

While the exact adoption strategy might vary between different use-cases based on the course's content, module design, and available technical means, generic recommendations can be provided. It is a recommended practice to divide the content into multiple smaller modules and create a corresponding digital credential for each one. This provides participants with an instant tangible

achievement as they progress through the course's content. Additionally, by doing so, a digital credentials hierarchy can be constructed, using dependencies between different digital credentials where one acts as a prerequisite to others, thus following the natural flow of the content.

To confirm that a participant has successfully completed all parts of a course, a final digital credential can be issued. The concrete conditions for the issuing of this digital credential can vary between contexts, but commonly it is tied to the completion of all course modules, in addition to some performance benchmark, such as receiving a passing grade. To differentiate between different participants' performance levels, multiple, mutually exclusive, digital credentials can be defined. The exact steps for integrating the issuing of the digital credential with the learners' progress on the learning platform vary depending on whether Open Badges or EDCs are used. More details about both options are available in the subsections that follow.

Open Badges

Open Badges enjoy a wide support from many learning management platforms today [R19], allowing for automatic issuing of a badge once a course participant meets the specified criteria. This support allows course managers to design and integrate Open Badges in their courses without any additional support from the platform administrators, assuming that the respective Open Badges has been enabled at the platform level.

To ease the process of designing and implementing granular badges for a given course for course managers, multiple badge templates have been developed as part of the Skills4EOSC project. These templates can be freely reused and adapted for creating concrete badge implementations. The templates follow the outlined recommendations above and can be immediately used for implementing a badge hierarchy. In total, there are 4 specialist badges and 6 submodule badges. Instruction on when to use each badge are provided below:

- The instructor badge is to be used for Training of Trainers (ToT) courses and should be issued once the participant has successfully completed the whole course.

- The expert badge is to be used for regular training, and it depicts the highest performance level. The badge should be issued upon completion of the whole course.
- The graduated badge is to be used for regular training, and it depicts a mid-performance level. The badge should be issued upon completion of the whole course.
- The beginner badge is to be used for regular training, and it depicts the lowest performance level. The badge should be issued upon completion of the whole course.
- The remaining 6 submodule badges have different colour schemes, but their purpose is the same – they are to be used for recognizing the successful completion of concrete parts of the learning content.

Providing the badge templates as a PowerPoint document allows them to be easily edited in place, since all of the content is formatted in dedicated text boxes which are easy to alter. In most cases, the following placeholder text needs to be manually adjusted within the badge image itself:

- Training Name (for all badges) – to be replaced with the name of the course for which the badge is issued.
- Submodule (only for the 6 submodule related badge templates) – the name of the submodule whose completion will result in the issuing of the badge.

Once the badge has been designed, the next step would be to define it in the badge issuing platform of choice. No matter the adopted technical solution (such as a dedicated badge platform or a complete learning management system), the principles remain the same: a badge image together with accompanying metadata needs to be provided. Then, badge issuing criteria need to be formally defined. This makes the badge definition a multi-step process.

The first step is to provide the basic information about the badge such as: name, version, language, description, image, image attribution information, and an optional badge expiry date. Specific information for some of the fields is available below. If a field is not explicitly mentioned, it is up to the course administrator to choose a suitable value, as they see fit.

- Version – used for keeping track of multiple iterations of a badge. Please note that once created a badge cannot be edited in place, so keeping track

of versions becomes important. During the initial creation it is recommended to assign a 1.0.0 version number and increment it in the future, as modifications are made.

- Image – the badge image as exported from PowerPoint using a format supported by the target platform.
- Image author’s name – the preferred value for this field in case the badge is created using the project’s badge templates is “Skills4EOSC project”.
- Image author’s email - the preferred value for this field in case the badge is created using the project’s badge templates is “info@lists.skills4eosc.eu”.
- Image author’s URL - the preferred value for this field in case the badge is created using the project’s badge templates is “https://www.skills4eosc.eu/”.

The next steps are to define the issuing criteria for the badge, as well as to make it publicly available and visible to participants, thus allowing them to obtain it. These steps are strongly dependent on the learning platform where the badges are created. In the text that follows we will focus on Moodle, one of the most popular open-source learning management systems, used across many projects, universities, and MOOCs, including the Skills4EOSC learning platform. Other systems should follow a similar workflow, but the terminology might differ to some extent.

A badge can have multiple issuing criteria associated with it, such as “manual issue by role” as well as “activity completion” or “course completion”. Manual issue by role allows the badge to be issued on purpose by a privileged user that is a member of the course, usually a teacher. This option is useful when course administrators want to have the flexibility to issue badges by themselves. This can optionally be the only method to obtain the badge, applied after manually verifying that a given course participant has successfully completed the corresponding submodule or course. Alternatively, it can be used in addition to other, automated, issuing methods once certain course activities have been marked as completed. What “completed” means ultimately depends on the type of the activity. For files this can mean that the user has simply opened the corresponding link on the course page. For other more interactive activities such as quizzes and assignments, it can mean successful submission by the student or having received a passing grade.

Once the badge definition has been concluded, the badge should be enabled, so that course participants can start their work towards obtaining it. If enabling a badge on an already active course where some participants might already have fulfilled the badge issuing criteria, verify with the platform administrator whether the badge will automatically be issued retroactively. In most cases this holds true, Moodle included.

After a badge has been obtained by a participant, they will receive a notification either via email or via the learning platform's alerting system. Participants should be encouraged to sync their badges to their own backpack, leveraging the backpack integration at the learning management system level (if present and enabled by the platform's administrator). Alternatively, the badge can simply be downloaded from the badge issuing platform and then manually uploaded to the backpack platform of choice.

European Digital Credentials

Currently, we refer to the [Guidelines created in the DocTalen4EU project](#). Guidelines from Skills4EOSC will be included in an addendum to this deliverable once the Skills4EOSC EDC pilot has been completed.

7.3 The platform administrator's perspective

The platform administrators should carefully consider the advantages and disadvantages of each option before implementing them in practice. Depending on the chosen approach, a tighter or more loose integration with the learning management systems where the learners conduct the activities, can be chosen. Verification and longevity requirements also play an important role as both Open Badges and EDCs have different approaches to these aspects. In the subsections that follow, more specific advice and recommendations for adopting either of these technologies is provided.

Open Badges

As a platform administrator, the first step towards adopting the Open Badges aspects of the Framework is to verify that the learning platform where the learning content is to be hosted has native support for the Open Badges specification, while also considering the supported version number, as the difference in

functionality is quite significant. The popularity of Open Badges has led many open-source and proprietary learning platforms today to offer first party support [R19]. Another major aspect that needs to be covered is to decide on the level of integration with Open Badges, namely whether badges will only be displayed on the learning platform or will they be issued by it as well. The available options for issuing badges are either to designate the learning platform itself as an issuer, or use an external, third-party service for this task. Caution needs to be exercised during this decision, weighing the pros and cons of each approach. A third-party service acting as an issuer might require complex integrations with the learning platform and might incur additional cost. On the other hand, it might provide a more reliable infrastructure, allowing the badges to be verifiable even if the original learning platform is no longer available.

An important thing to note when it comes to verifiability of the issued badges is that depending on the version used of the Open Badges specification, two verification methods might be supported: signed badges and hosted badges [R27]. In the signed version, available as of Open Badges 3.0 [R28], the badges are signed with a digital signature, ensuring that they are tamper evident and allowing for self-contained verification (no external third party is contacted during the verification process). On the other hand, hosted badges are easier to implement, and they embed a link to the issuer's website. During the verification process, this website is contacted to verify the authenticity of the embedded metadata in the Open Badge. Since the administrator of the issuer's website has full control over it, this can potentially raise concerns over the authenticity of hosted badges. Additionally, it also has an impact on the longevity of the issued badge, since it requires that the issuer's website is continuously available, otherwise the badge would be invalid.

To facilitate easier badge sharing and to simplify the process for creating a personal badge portfolio for the learners, integration with one or more online backpack services can be considered. Many free backpack services for hosted badges exist today, offering programmatic integration with learning platforms, allowing users to easily sync obtained badges to such third-party services. Attention should also be paid to the layout of the course pages, allowing available badges as well as the relevant criteria to be prominently featured and visible to

all participants. Alternatively, signed badges can be added to the upcoming digital wallet applications, as discussed previously.

Finally, it is important to take into account that in the case when hosted badges are used, the validity of the badge is tied to the issuing platform itself, which is automatically contacted by any online validators during badge verifications. Administrators should ensure the continuous availability of the system, thus keeping the issued badges valid.

European Digital Credentials

Currently, we refer to the [Guidelines created in the DocTalen4EU project](#). Guidelines from Skills4EOSC will be included in an addendum to this deliverable once the Skills4EOSC EDC pilot has been completed.

7.4 Acquisition of Qualified Electronic Seal: GARR's experience and recommendations

The procurement of a qualified electronic seal for the implementation of the European Digital Credentials for Learning presented significant administrative challenges that required careful planning and considerable time investment. As a public administration, GARR was required to conduct the procurement through MEPA (Mercato Elettronico_ della Pubblica Amministrazione), Italy's electronic marketplace for public administrations.

The procurement process highlighted several important considerations. First, the legal implications of becoming a credential issuer required extensive internal discussions and management approval. GARR's management raised concerns about the legal responsibilities associated with credential issuance, particularly regarding liability and compliance with EU regulations. These concerns necessitated a thorough review and documentation of responsibilities, adding complexity to the process.

Additionally, it is crucial to carefully select the supplier, as there were notable price differences between vendors. A thorough comparison of suppliers is necessary to ensure cost-effectiveness and compliance with requirements.

Based on this experience, we strongly recommend that organisations planning to implement EDC with qualified electronic seals start the procurement process as early as possible. Early engagement with management and proactive planning can help streamline implementation.

While Skills4EOSC's decision to implement EDC came later in the project timeline, GARR's procurement demonstrates that mid-project implementation is possible, though it requires careful time management. This experience underscores the importance of allowing sufficient time for administrative procedures and management discussions when planning EDC implementation.

To facilitate smoother implementation in future projects, we recommend:

- Including EDC implementation plans in initial project proposals where possible
- Initiating management commitment and legal discussions as early as possible
- Allowing for extended procurement timelines, especially when working within public administration frameworks
- Clearly documenting the legal implications and responsibilities of issuing credentials
- Building in contingency time for unexpected administrative delays
- Conducting a thorough comparison of suppliers to ensure cost-effectiveness and compliance with requirements

Annex 1 Landscaping results (CNRS)

Results from landscaping of material relevant to recognition and accreditation.

<i>Project / Training</i>	<i>Summary</i>	<i>Lessons</i>
RDA	The Research Data Alliance has defined several standards that are relevant for Skills4EOSC, the most relevant one being the Minimal Metadata Schema for Learning Resources [R29].	The Minimal metadata schema for learning material is already being used in Skills4EOSC.
OBERRED	OBERRED [R30] was a European Erasmus+ project (2019-2022) aimed at creating an Open Badge ecosystem for recognising skills in sharing research data in the field of open science.	Open Badges require minimal technical effort to be implemented in practice, allowing every institution to easily use badges as a certification method within their courses.
The Carpentries	The Carpentries [R31] have a train-the-trainer model that is certified and highly recognised.	The Carpentries have a strong brand within the community. This is also an established legal entity that can develop their brand and issue certificates.
RltrainPlus	RltrainPlus [R32] have a train the trainer model and are working to have European-wide recognition for these courses.	RltrainPlus is working to set up recognised micro-credentials among University charter. However, this work is currently in its early stages and at the moment issues only Open Badges.

NI4OS-Europe	In NI4OS-Europe [R33], a combination of train-the-trainer and national end-users and capacity building trainings were delivered using a Moodle-based learning platform that has been extended to support the RDA minimal metadata schema for learning materials, enabling them to import the training information into the EOSC catalogue.	NI4OS-Europe offers a user-friendly FAIR learning environment providing a mix of self-paced courses and training materials in different languages including learning paths and open badges with automated issuing.
NASA Open Science Certification under TOPS initiative (Transform to Open Science)	The NASA TOPS initiative [R34] is a community developed course offered via a MOOC.	They will issue Open Science Badges for their in-person and virtual courses. They are using Open Badges as the technical solution to issue the badges.
EC work on Micro-credentials	On 16 June 2022, the Council of the European Union (EU) adopted a Recommendation on a European approach to micro-credentials for lifelong learning and employability [R35]. Several initiatives for implementation of the recommendation have since been started.	The format of the Skills4EOSC courses seems to fit with the idea of low-volume micro-credentials. Open Badges is one of the technology stacks that is recommended for implementation of micro-credentials.
Europass/ European Digital Credentials for learning	European Digital Credentials for learning (EDC) [R36] is the main EC initiative for handling digital credentials. These	The Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework should fit into the Europass/EDC framework.

	are standardised tamper-evident electronic documents describing that their owner has certain skills or has achieved certain learning outcomes through formal, non-formal or informal learning context.	
Open Data Institute (ODI)	ODI [R37] offers a number of paid training courses, including a programme based on the train-the-trainers model. ODI uses the term "registered trainers" to designate trainers who have obtained a certification.	As ODI's courses are not free, we don't know much about the platform's certification process or the tool it uses to certify skills.
EOSC Future	The EOSC Future project [R38] has developed training material aimed at training stakeholders to become active users and providers of EOSC and to increase uptake of EOSC resources. An important part of this is to support providers to add their resources in the EOSC Portal.	EOSC Future issues digital badges based on the Open Badges standard.
LINUX Professional Institute - LPI	The LPI [R39] offers a long range of courses for open-source developers. The certificates are valid for 5 years. Description of the technical solution for issuing the certificates not	The LPI offers more formal education than is planned for the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework. Additionally, it is not clear if their work is based on open standards.

	found.	
International Computer Driving Licence - Europe	The ICDL is an international organisation for basic digital skills. A special version has been developed for Europe [R40]. It is based on the educa learning platform [R41]. We were unable to find information on digital certificates.	The ICDL offers more formal than we are planning and not, as far as we can see, based on open standards.
Digital Credentials 4 EU - DC4EU	The European Commission will provide a prototype of an EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDI) [R42] as set out in the proposed European Digital Identity Regulation. A pilot for including digital credentials in the wallet will be part of the DC4EU project [R43] under the Digital Europe programme.	The project plans to implement mappings for several digital credential formats, including EDC and Open Badges. The wallets that are to be implemented on a national level are designed to recognise both EDCs and OBs as forms of digital credentials that can be stored in the wallet and then shared with other parties based on the needs of the wallet holder.
DocTalent4EU	DocTalent4EU [R14, R44] aims to enhance PhD employability through a strong, visible and innovative recognition-system of the most in-demand transferable skills that early-career researchers acquire or will acquire through their doctoral training and research activities.	DocTalent4EU has chosen European Digital Credentials as the main technical solution for their courses' digital credentials. They have also written two easy to follow guides on how to issue and use EDC [R44].

<p>Open Science Learning Gate</p>	<p>The Open Science Learning Gate [R45] is an initiative from the Network for Education and Research Quality (NERQ) [R46] that aims to provide Open Science training for many of the same profiles that are covered in Skills4EOSC.</p>	<p>Established June 2024. Skills4EOSC is establishing contact to explore possibilities for cooperation.</p>
<p>Digital Credentials Consortium</p>	<p>The Digital Credentials Consortium (DCC) [R47] was founded in 2018 by leading universities with expertise in the design of verifiable digital credentials. Their mission is to create a trusted, distributed, and shared infrastructure that will become the standard for issuing, storing, displaying, and verifying academic credentials, digitally.</p>	<p>The DCC maintains open-source software and code libraries to issue verifiable academic digital credentials. The work of the DCC is valuable though still in development phase. It also requires IT/infrastructure support within institutions.</p>
<p>CHARM ALLIANCE</p>	<p>The CHARM ALLIANCE, a European University co-funded by the Erasmus+ program, is exploring modern and innovative approaches to recognize knowledge and skills. As part of this effort, Trinity College Dublin has been tasked with investigating the use of digital badges for CHARM EU.</p>	<p>CHARM EU piloted digital badges using the edubadges platform. Based on this successful first pilot, the EDCL was selected to carry out a second pilot. These efforts reflect the project's innovative commitment to using digital badges as a way to recognize, validate, and reward professional skills.</p>

References

No	Description/Link
R1	European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a European approach to micro-credentials for lifelong learning and employability, December 2021
R2	Shields, Rebecca, and Ritesh Chugh. "Digital badges–rewards for learning?." <i>Education and Information Technologies</i> 22 (2017): 1817-1824.
R3	Clements, Kyle, Richard Edward West, and Enoch Hunsaker. "Getting started with open badges and open microcredentials." <i>The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning</i> 21.1 (2020): 154-172.
R4	1EdTech, IMS Global Learning Consortium, Open Badges Specifications (accessed November 25, 2024)
R5	EOSC-A, The EOSC Partnership Monitoring Framework, V6.6, March 2022
R6	Whyte, A. et al. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo.
R7	Filiposka, S., at al. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials (1.4). Zenodo.
R8	Sánchez, M., at al. (2023). D2.3 Community-endorsed quality assurance and certification framework for professional training and qualifications (1.3). Zenodo.
R9	European Commission EMPL, European Learning Model, GitHub repo
R10	Deliverable co-creation survey (accessed November 2024)
R11	RDC EU Europass, What are Digital Credentials, https://europass.europa.eu/en/what-are-digital-credentials
R12	About 1EdTech Consortium (accessed on February 22, 2025)
R13	Europass official website (accessed on February 22, 2025)
R14	European university foundation, DocTalent4EU project, co-funded by the Horizon EUROPE programme
R15	EU EDC pages under Europass tools (accessed January 2025)
R16	Skills4EOSC Learning Platform, FAIR-by-Design Learning Materials Methodology Training, 17-19 October 2023
R17	Canvas Badges, Badgr, all-in-one digital badging
R18	Online Credential Builder for EDCs (accessed January 2025)
R19	OA5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling

R20	List of platforms supporting Open Badges and accredited by1EdTech (accessed on February 22, 2025)
R21	List of certified hosting tools for Open Badges (accessed January 2025)
R22	How to add badges to your EuroPass CV (accessed January 2025)
R23	Open Badges Platform (linkedIn) (accessed January 2025)
R24	Badgr Open Badges 2.0 Validator (accessed November 25, 2024)
R25	IMS Global Open Badges 2.0 Validator (accessed November 25, 2024)
R26	Open Badges Specification, Assertion Issuance to Wallet (accessed January 2025)
R27	EU Digital Identity Wallet (accessed January 2025)
R28	Verifiable Credentials Support Increases Learner Data Privacy and Trustworthiness of Open Badges (accessed January 2025)
R29	Open Badges Specification 3.0 (accessed February 22nd 2025)
R30	Hoebelheinrich, N. J., et al. (2022). <i>Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources (Version 1.0)</i>. Research Data Alliance.
R31	Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of Skills in Research Data Management & Sharing - OBERRED European Erasmus+ project
R32	The Carpentries , fiscally sponsored project of Community Initiatives
R33	RltrainPlus project, funded by the European Union's H2020 programme under grant agreement no.101008503
R34	The National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe (NI4OS-Europe) project, funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 European research infrastructures grant agreement no. 857645
R35	NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS) initiative
R36	General Secretariat of the EC Council, Adoption of the Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a European approach to micro-credentials for lifelong learning and employability, May 2022
R37	Europass, European Digital Credentials for learning, Europass digital tools (accessed on November 25, 2024)
R38	The Open Data Institute (accessed on November 25, 2024)
R39	The EOSC Future project, co-funded by the European Union Horizon Programme call INFRAEOSC-03-2020 - Grant Agreement Number 101017536
R40	Linux Professional Institute (LPI), non-profit, global certification standard and career support organization for open source professionals
R41	ICDL Europe (accessed on November 25, 2024)

R42	Educa learning platform (accessed on November 25, 2024)
R43	EU Digital Identity Wallet Pilot implementation, July 2023
R44	Digital Credentials for Europe - DC4E project, co-funded by the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101102611
R45	Manual for DocTalen4EU credentials issuing
R46	Open Science Learning Gate Initiative (accessed November 2024)
R47	Network for Education and Research Quality (NERQ) (accessed February 2025)